

8T – N-Tuples

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting which allowed the author to derive the primordial equation of coupling magnitudes under the mathematical notion of an "N-Tuple", i.e. an ordered set of elements, it is possible to expand the idea of a Boson as a product of an N-tuple.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equation (1.2A). By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the idea of an N-tuple, which is an ordered set of elements. To start the analysis one will change the setting using functor, from a varying manifold onto a set.

$$\Lambda: Top \rightarrow Set$$

Each prime pair used in the original derivation now stand as a set of elements. One mentioned that the number of primes could be infinite, for simplicity sake, two was chosen. The criteria one was asking is the prime pair sum to be two and three devisable. So to put the idea mathematically:

$$N = (\mathcal{P}_1 \dots \mathcal{P}_n)$$

$$N_s = (\mathcal{P}_1 + \mathcal{P}_2 + \dots \mathcal{P}_n)$$

$$[2, 3] \mid N_s$$

We have defined the Boson to be a prime amount of net variation, which arises from the N-Tuple, in an amount proportional to the average of the N-Tuple.

$$\frac{N_s}{N} \propto N_V$$

to expand the idea of a Boson using N Tuple, we can associate the Boson to be a product type of the N-Tuple. The Boson is the product of the N-Tuple that satisfy the devisors requirements. So to put it mathematically.

$$N_V = \prod_{\phi=1}^{\phi=N_V} \delta g_{\phi} = \delta g_{\phi=1} \times \delta g_{\phi=2} \times \delta g_{\phi=3} \quad (1.23)$$

$$\delta g_{\phi=1} \equiv \delta g_{\phi=2} \equiv \delta g_{\phi=3}$$

Since in contrast to Fermions we have only one sign for Boson, positive summation of curvature, or negative if we consider:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = -2Ric \quad (1.23.A)$$

So according to this idea, the subscript is mere index that counts the number of times the arbitrary curvature is chained. The difference among the Bosons is the number of chained arbitrary variations. As an example the difference among the photon with $N_V = +5$ and the W^- with $N_V = +3$ would be:

$$\begin{aligned} W^- &= \delta g_{\phi=1} \times \delta g_{\phi=2} \times \delta g_{\phi=3} \\ \gamma &= \delta g_{\phi=1} \times \delta g_{\phi=2} \times \delta g_{\phi=3} \times \delta g_{\phi=4} \times \delta g_{\phi=5} \\ \delta g_{\phi=4} &\equiv \delta g_{\phi=5} \equiv \delta g_{\phi=1} \end{aligned}$$

since all the terms are prime number multiples, if we consider (1.63) they are negative amount of curvature, the difference between each Boson is the number of elements in the term of (1.23). that is the analog of the original idea made in March. The prime pairs are N-tuples, which has products of prime type of the same element in different amount.

$$[2, 3] \neq \prod_{\phi=1}^{\phi=N_V} \delta g_{\phi} \quad (1.24)$$

So using the idea of N-tuples it is easier to grasp the difference among Fermions, which arise in even numbers of two distinct elements which differ in sign and summed as zero, as (1.48) indicate. From those summations, product type may rise, which are proportional to the average size of the summation, those product type has one element which has a negative sign, and the different products differ in the number of times this element is multiplied, as (1.23) indicate. Since the number of repetition is prime, the more repetitions we have, the weaker the element, since the photon has five times versus three times for the W Boson, it yields, assuming $\delta g_{\phi} \in \mathbb{R}$ a bigger negative number, or if we assume that $\delta g_{\phi} < 1$ and positive, a smaller positive number as the repetitions increase. Those assumptions rely of the idea that δg_{ϕ} is a curvature spike which can be quantified.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad